

**ABBREVIATION AS WORD
FORMATION PROCESS IN ENGLISH
CONTRASTIVE WITH ALBANIAN**

Morphology

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Abstract

It is known that every language possesses its philosophy. Nowadays, there are approximately 6,500 languages that are spoken in the world. Every each of them has their own functions and usage. This structured scheme makes the communication between people a lot easier. It is also well known that the grammar of a foreign language can not be taught and understood well, if we don't know the grammar of our own native language. And by this, we understand that between all these languages there are differences and similarities, which makes the grammar part more complex. The aim of this paper is to describe the word formation as a process of forming new words, as well as, a brief analysis of abbreviation in English language compared with the abbreviation in Albanian language.

The speakers of a certain language usually take for granted the existence of words. To understand a language and its rules actually means knowing the words of that language. New words come to our minds and our language on a daily basis.

A word is something spoken orally and uttered through a sound or group of sounds that indicates a meaning, description, place, time, news, or thought. Words are created of one or more morphemes and they are the smallest units adaptable of independent use. The word being one of the smallest units is not accompanied with the credibility that it should have, however communication wouldn't have been possible without it. We can see its importance and how significant the word is by the way we use it in a sentence, starting from a complex sentence to a single word standing on its own and still making sense.

After explaining briefly what a word is, logically and automatically a definition about Word-formation is created in the human mind; which is as follows: the process of forming new words. A very simple definition but in the same time very effective. This process of forming new words has also its processes which will be mentioned eventually throughout the paper, not only in English but as well as in Albanian Language.

Word formation

In the fourth century, Panini provided a detailed description of word-formation in Sanskrit which is widely known as the earliest evidence of curiosity in vocabulary.⁴ The process of forming new words on the basis of other morphemes or words is likely known as word formation. It indicates either a state or a process, and it can be perceived either diachronically (via different periods of history) or synchronically (a particular period in time).

⁴ <https://www.oposinet.com/temario-de-ingles-secundaria/temario-2-ingles-secundaria/topic-10-the-lexicon-characteristics-of-word-formation-in-english-prefixation-suffixation-composition/>

The English vocabulary can also be enriched by using old lexemes in forming new ones by: combining them to form compounds, converting their word class or adding affixes to the previous existing forms. Fischer (1998) gives the following definition of Word -formation: "A Word-formation is a word, which has lost its status of a nonce-formation but is still the one, which is considered as new by the majority of members of a speech community". A nonce-formation is a word, which is created and used by a speaker who believes it to be new (Bauer, 1983); once a speaker is aware of having used or heard a word before, it ceases to be a nonce-formation. The newly coined words are constantly introduced into a language (Algeo, 1980; Lehrer, 1996), often for naming a new concept. Domains that are culturally prominent contain new words. Concepts, which are rapidly advancing, (for example electronic communication and the Internet) also take help of Word-formation strategies. New expressions and novel words do arise throughout a language (Ayto, 1990, Knowles and Elliott, 1997).⁵ When dealing with the creation of new words it can be noticed that besides the morphological factors there are past factors continuing up to the present day. The historical events that can be mentioned in the process of enriching the vocabulary are: the science growth in the field of chemistry, astronomy, medicine, and physics. In coining of new words mass media and internet have also contributed with unique terms originating from all areas of knowledge.

Word formation processes

After the linguistic and historical framework of word-formation is given, a logical preparation of theoretical approach for word- formation can be provided. According to "Word-formation in English" by Ingo Plag, there are two main word-formation processes in English language: 1) major word-formation processes which include compounding, derivation and conversion; and 2) minor word-formation processes which include blending, clipping, backformation, acronymy, abbreviation.

Derivation, builds new words by adding morphemes to stems. These morphemes are added to the target stem by affixation, through prefixes and suffixes. While prefixes like un- or disusually do not change the lexical category of a word, suffixes, such as -ness, -ment, -ing, or -ation, usually do. If you take the examples employ, employment, unemployment.⁶

Compounding is the process of putting words together to build a new one that "does not denote two things, but one" and that is "pronounced as one unit". English examples would be bookcase (book + case), textbook (text+book), and wastebasket (waste+basket).⁷

Clipping - is the of word formation process which is made of the trimming of a word to one of its parts. They are also known as shortenings. For example: *advertisement* (ad), *exam* (examination), *chute* (parachute), *flu* (influenza).

⁵ <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/144526769.pdf>

⁶ <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v4i7/SUB156217.pdf>

⁷ <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v4i7/SUB156217.pdf>

Blending - is a word formation created from parts of two already known or existing words. For example: brunch is a blend of breakfast and lunch; dawk for dove and hawk; motel for motor and hotel.⁸

Back-formation - a process that creates a word by removing the affix. For example: enthuse for enthusiasm; televise for television; lase for laser.⁹

Acronymy - words formed by taking the initial letters of the words in a phrase and reading them as a word: e.g. NATO for North Atlantic Treaty Organisation; MA for Master of Arts.¹⁰

Abbreviation - is a word formation process known as a shortened form of a written word or phrase. They are used to save space and also time and to keep us away from repeating the long words. Some abbreviations can be formed by excluding all except some of the first letters of a word like: Oct for October, uni for university. Other abbreviations can be formed by excluding letters from the middle of the word like: govt-government, Dr. for Doctor. The difference between **abbreviation** and is that; an acronym is a shortened form of a word and is usually made up of the initial letters of that word. For example, **NATO** comes from “North Atlantic Treaty Organization,” and **ASAP** comes from “as soon as possible.” Abbreviations, on the other hand, can be shortened forms of words or phrases, and need not necessarily be made up of the initial letters of either. **ASAP** and **appt** (for **appointment**) are both considered abbreviations, but only **ASAP** is an acronym. Acronyms are a type of abbreviation.¹¹

Word formation in Albanian

Word formation is one of the ways that a vocabulary of the standard language can be seen. Both of these two languages Albanian and English belong to the Indo-European language but of course they do have differences between one another. They have their own originality. The origin of the Albanian language is very well pronounced. It has a big number of affixes which can be very effective in forming new words. It has got about 170 suffixes (Xhuvani, Çabej, 1976, p.53) and about 80 prefixes. Even English is rich in affixes which are very active in forming new words nowadays. According to “*Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe*” published by the Institute of Linguistics and Literature and the Academy of Science of Albania, the ways in which the words are formed is: 1) Derivation, 2) articulation, 3) composition, 4) compounding, 5) conversion. Some other Albanian linguists classify the Albanian words in different ways, for example, the Albanian linguists Agalliu, Demiraj and Domi make another grouping of the ways of word-formation: 1. Morphological methods which include affixation, articulation and composition; 2. Non-morphological methods that are compounding and conversion.¹²

⁸ Stefanovski L “English lexicology”

⁹ Stefanovski L “English lexicology”

¹⁰ Stefanovski L “English lexicology”

¹¹ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/abbreviation>

¹² <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v4i7/SUB156217.pdf>

In both languages the definitions of these word formation processes are the same, and with the fact that this seminar paper is mostly about abbreviation, it will proceed with its definition in Albanian and its characteristics. In the book of Mehmet Çeliku abbreviation is said to be a special type of composition which means words created from two or more shortened words united.

There are two types of short compositions:

1. The syllable type (Tipi rrokjesor) When the two first syllables of a word unite; mapo (magazine popullore), Profarma (prodhime farmaceutike). This type of composition isn't productive.

2. The starter type (tipi nistor) which is divided into three subtypes: a) Nistor-shkronjor, in this subtype the words are formed from the mixture of the two first letters of the given phrase such as: ATSH, BGSJ, FMN, SMT. b) Nistor-tingullor, this subtype is formed by merging the first sounds of the given phrase or word like; DEBATIK, TEC, KEMP, and NATO. c) Nëntipi i perzier, (shkronjor-tingullor ose tingullor-shkronjor): NTUS (nëtëus), NTAN (nëtëan).¹³

Other examples for abbreviations in Albanian language:

Ana.	Anatomia
Bakt.	Bakteriologjia
Dipl.	Diplomacia
Foto.	Fotografia
Kinem.	Kinematografia
Mat.	Matematika
P.e.s	Para erës sonë

Conclusion

In conclusion, both of the languages have a word formation capability by using different types of processes. Even though English language has had an enormous effect in enriching the Albanian language by borrowings they still have some differences regarding this topic. As for the grammatical aspect it can be said that the Albanian language is mostly a synthetic-analytic language while English is the opposite analytic-synthetic. The difference which shows up in the abbreviation process is that the English language has a simpler aspect towards it while in the Albanian language we had some subtypes which were a part of abbreviation. Lastly but not least, it has been mentioned in the Albanian books that abbreviation is a part of the composition which also is a word formation process where as in English abbreviation is a word formation on its own. Apart from that acronyms were kind of a type of abbreviation which might create a small similarity with the Albanian language. The aim of this paper was to describe the word formation as a process of forming new words, as well as, a brief analysis of abbreviation in English language compared with the abbreviation in Albanian language.

¹³ Mehmet Çeliku. Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe II, Sintaksa. P.74

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